

Odd Perfect Numbers Do Not Exist.

Tony Kuria Kimani

tkimani19@gmail.com

Student, Msc. Research Methodology

Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology

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Abstract

An odd perfect number N is a number whose sum of divisors is equal to $2N$. Euler proved that if an odd perfect number exists then it must have the form $p^x q^2$. Where p is a prime number and p and x are of the form $1 \pmod{4}$. This paper proves that odd perfect numbers do not exist

Introduction

In this paper, deficiency of x will be denoted by $D(x) = 2x - \sigma(x)$

The sum of proper divisors of x will be denoted by $s(x) = \sigma(x) - x$

The sum of divisors of x will be denoted by $\sigma(x)$

and the abundancy index of x will be denoted by $I(x) = \frac{\sigma(x)}{x}$

I was reading a question asked by Arnie Bebita Dris (Dris, 2022) on Math Stack Exchange. He was working on a particular problem on odd perfect numbers and he came up with an equation from which I realized I could obtain a contradiction. In this paper I will derive a contradiction from Dris' equation. This contradiction will prove that odd perfect numbers do not exist.

Dris' Equation

In this section, I will reproduce Dris' equation as it appears on the Math Stack Exchange website (with only minor changes in notation).

If $p^x q^2$ is an odd perfect number with p being the special prime then the following equation is known to be true (Dris, 2021).

$$\frac{2q^2}{\sigma(p^x)} = p\sigma(q^2) - 2(p-1)q^2 \quad (1)$$

Dividing both sides by pq^2 we get:

$$\frac{2}{p\sigma(p^x)} = I(q^2) - \frac{2(p-1)}{p} \quad (2)$$

Which implies that the reciprocal of $I(q^2) - \frac{2(p-1)}{p}$ is an integer since $\frac{p\sigma(p^x)}{2}$ is an integer. Equation 2 is what I call Dris' equation and its reciprocal is supposed to be an integer. This is where Dris left the equation and he did not proceed to prove that $I(q^2) - \frac{2(p-1)}{p}$ cannot be an integer. In this paper I will prove that $I(q^2) - \frac{2(p-1)}{p}$ cannot be an integer hence contradicting the requirement that it must be an integer.

Theorem 1: If $p^x q^2$ is an odd perfect number with p being the special prime then $I(q^2) - \frac{2(p-1)}{p}$ cannot be an integer

Proof:

$$I(q^2) - \frac{2(p-1)}{p} = \frac{I(q^2)p - 2(p-1)}{p} = \frac{I(q^2)p - 2p + 2}{p} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{I(q^2)p - 2p + 2}{p} = \frac{[I(q^2) - 2]p + 2}{p} = \frac{[\frac{\sigma(q^2)}{q^2} - 2]p + 2}{p} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{[\frac{\sigma(q^2)}{q^2} - 2]p + 2}{p} = \frac{[\frac{\sigma(q^2) - 2q^2}{q^2}]p + 2}{p} = \frac{[\frac{-D(q^2)}{q^2}]p + 2}{p} \quad (5)$$

The fraction $\frac{-D(q^2)}{q^2}$ can be simplified as follows:

$$\frac{-D(q^2)}{q^2} = \frac{-s(p^x) \times \gcd(q^2, \sigma(q^2))}{\frac{\sigma(p^x)}{2} \times \gcd(q^2, \sigma(q^2))} = \frac{-s(p^x)}{\frac{\sigma(p^x)}{2}} \quad (6)$$

Equation 5 then becomes:

$$\frac{[\frac{-s(p^x)}{\frac{\sigma(p^x)}{2}}]p + 2}{p} = \frac{[\frac{-s(p^x)p}{\frac{\sigma(p^x)}{2}}] + 2}{p} \quad (7)$$

It is known that:

$$-s(p^x)p = -\sigma(p^x) + 1 \quad (8)$$

Therefore:

$$\frac{\left[\frac{-s(p^x)p}{\sigma(p^x)}\right] + 2}{p} = \frac{\left[\frac{-\sigma(p^x)+1}{\sigma(p^x)}\right] + 2}{p} = \frac{\left[\frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)}\right] + 2}{p} \quad (9)$$

This means that:

$$I(q^2) - \frac{2(p-1)}{p} = \frac{\left[\frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)}\right] + 2}{p} \quad (10)$$

Since the reciprocal of $I(q^2) - \frac{2(p-1)}{p}$ must be an integer, this therefore means that the reciprocal of $\frac{\left[\frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)}\right] + 2}{p}$ must also be an integer.

$$\frac{p}{\left[\frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)}\right] + 2} = \text{an integer.} \quad (11)$$

But we know that p is a prime number which means that p is only divisible by 1 and p itself. Therefore, if $\left[\frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)}\right] + 2$ is a positive integer then it must be equal to either 1 or p . If $\left[\frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)}\right] + 2$ is a negative integer then it must be equal to either -1 or $-p$. Therefore we can say that:

$$\left[\frac{-2\sigma(p^x) + 2}{\sigma(p^x)} \right] + 2 = \pm 1 \quad \text{or} \quad \pm p \quad (12)$$

Now, notice that:

$$-2 < \left[\frac{-2\sigma(p^x) + 2}{\sigma(p^x)} \right] < -1 \quad (13)$$

This is true because we know for a fact that $\sigma(p^x) > 2$.

This means that $\left[\frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)} \right]$ cannot be an integer because it is a number located between two consecutive integers.

If $\left[\frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)} \right]$ is not an integer then $\left[\frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)} \right] + 2$ is also not an integer because an integer plus a non-integer cannot result in an integer. But this is a contradiction since in equation 12 we said that $\left[\frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)} \right] + 2$ must be an integer of the form ± 1 or $\pm p$.

This contradiction means that an odd perfect number does not exist.

Q.E.D.

Postscript:

Can we actually tell whether $\left[\frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)} \right] + 2$ is a positive or a negative number? Using equation

13, it is easy to see that $\lceil \frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)} \rceil + 2$ is in fact a positive number. This therefore means that $\lceil \frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)} \rceil + 2$ must either be 1 or p . However, I have already proven that $\lceil \frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)} \rceil + 2$ is not an integer. In fact, the following inequality is true: $0 < \lceil \frac{-2\sigma(p^x)+2}{\sigma(p^x)} \rceil + 2 < 1$. Hence the contradiction.

References

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